

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Comparative thermal performance investigation of the straight tube and square tube solar water heater

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 19(01), 727-735

Publication history: Received on 02 June 2023; revised on 14 July 2023; accepted on 16 July 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.19.1.1388>

Abstract

Sustainable energy is a need and demand of time to overcome issues related to greenhouse emissions and climate change and the most easily available and sustainable energy is solar energy which can be used for heating, cooking, and power generation. The most common application of solar energy is water heating and such hot water is used for domestic and industrial purposes for such purposes solar water heater (SWH) is commonly used; in the present work, an attempt has been made by changing the shape of pipe of copper pipe which is commonly used in SWH from a circular cross-section to square and comparing the results of the proposed model with conventional one. The K-type thermocouples measure the temperature at various locations of the experimental setup.

Keywords: Solar Water Heater; K-type thermocouples; Straight Tube; Square Tube

1. Introduction

Solar energy is the most efficient alternative energy source. Due to the increasing demand for energy and the increasing cost of fossil fuels (i.e. gas or oil), solar energy is considered an attractive renewable energy source, which can be used to purify water at home and industry. Hot water accounts for nearly 20% of the total energy consumption of the average home. Solar water heating systems are the cheapest and most affordable clean energy for homeowners who can provide most of the hot water required by their families. SWH systems are usually very simple, using only sunlight to heat the water. A working fluid is exposed to a dark surface exposed to sunlight, causing the temperature of the liquid to rise. This liquid can be directly heated by water. The solar water heater is a device used to heat water and generate steam for domestic and industrial purposes using solar energy. Solar energy is energy that comes from the sun in the form of solar radiation in infinite quantities, when this solar radiation falls on an absorbing surface, it is then converted into heat, and this heat is used to heat water. This type of endothermic loses heat by radiation and convection. These losses increase rapidly as the temperature of the working fluid increases. Soteris A. Kalogirou [1] presented a study on different types of solar collectors and their applications. Samara Sadrin et al [2] focused on a method of replacing solar water heating systems. P. Rhushi Prasad et al. [3] studied the experimental analysis of the flat plate collector and compared the performance with the tracking receiver. Wattana Ratismith et al [4] described a passive collector design in which the outlet temperature is increased by reducing heat loss. Krisztina Uzuneanu et al. [5] described the optimal tilt angle for low-concentration solar collectors. R. Herrero et al. [6] Concentrated enhancement technique for flat plate liquid solar collectors. Mustafa AKTAS et al [7] obtained an experimental analysis of the optimal fin size, which can be used in solar system heat exchangers, was performed. K. Sivakumar et al. [8] designed a flat elliptical heat-pipe solar collector and tested it with a collector tilt angle of 11° from the horizontal. Kalogirou [9] labored on a comparison of the thermal overall performance of the photo voltaic water heater. Madani et al. [10] targeted a lookup titled heating options for residential structures in China: modern-day reputation and future outlook. Souliotis et al. [11] carried out a lookup on the photo voltaic water heating for social housing: power evaluation and existence cycle assessment. Fani et al [12]

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targeted photo voltaic assisted CCHP system, energetic, economic, and environmental analysis, case study: academic workplace buildings. Altoé et al. [13] labored on lookup of titled an evaluation of the monetary viability and greenhouse gasoline emissions savings ensuing from the use of solar water heaters in a standard Brazilian dwelling. Hossain et al. [14] furnished a lookup titled Thermal and financial evaluation of less expensive modified flat-plate photo voltaic water heater with parallel two-side serpentine flow. Şerban et al. [15] focused on a lookup titled Monetary and environmental evaluation of investing in photo voltaic water heating systems. Bouhal et al. [16] studied on lookup titled graph and thermal overall performance optimization of a pressured collective solar warm water manufacturing gadget in Morocco for strength saving in residential buildings. Ayadi et al [17] got outcomes from a lookup titled Contrast of photo voltaic thermal and photo voltaic electric powered house heating and cooling structures for structures in exceptional climatic regions. Alayi et al. [18] carried out a lookup titled thermal evaluation of parabolic trough attention photovoltaic/thermal machine for use in buildings. Jignesh A. Patel et al [19] developed a spiral image voltaic water heater to reflect on the consideration of thermal normal overall performance utilizing bettering turbulence in the waft and consider the outcomes with a straight tube image voltaic water heater. Hardik A. Parmar et al [20] based on the thermal universal overall performance of serpentine photograph voltaic water and sold the variant in effectivity rate with understanding to time. P.P.Patil et al [21] offer graph consideration of the photo voltaic water heaters to reap warm water for home and industrial applications. S. Jaisankar et al [22] studied a range of strategies to beautify the thermal effectivity in a photo voltaic water heater. In addition to this, a distinctive dialogue on the barriers of current research, lookup hole, and advised viable adjustments are made. Runsheng Tang et al [23] centered on inspecting outcomes of water temperature in the storage tank and peak distinction between collector loop connections at the tank on freeze safety of flat-plate collectors. Selmi et al. [24] performed a validated CFD mannequin for a flat plate photo voltaic water heater. M.Z.H. Khan [25] additionally performed experiments in photo voltaic heating gadgets for effectivity closer to sustainable development. H.I. Abu-Mulaweh [26] defined designing and improvement of photo voltaic water heating device experimental apparatus. A standardized checking-out technique is required for evaluating the effectiveness of extraordinary kinds of collectors and designing and determination of proper equipment. Sushil Tiwari et al [27] reviewed the variety of strategies recommended by a range of researchers to decorate the overall performance of photo voltaic water heaters. Ho et al. [28] carried out an experimental and theoretical evaluation of a recycling flat-plate photo voltaic water heater outfitted with rectangle conduits. D Prakash et al. [29] focused on the environment-friendly use of photo voltaic electricity via a new solar water heating scheme and the float of warmth in the indoor development is detained utilizing sufficient ceiling insulation material. S. Sathishkumar et al. [30] initiated to find out about the opportunity of the usage of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) to keep photo voltaic electricity and to use this electricity in the course of the nighttime to warmth water for home purposes. Ankit S. Gujrathi et al. [31] tried to use Ansys 15.0 Workbench software program to mannequin a Parabolic Trough Collector and the PTC has been meant for an awareness ratio of 25. TR Bajracharya et al. [32] fabricated two panels collector with every having a fine vicinity of 1.55 m² and a hundred liters ability storage tank. Zhand and Malla [33] designed and developed a photo voltaic water heater (SWH) to generate and shop warm water beneath intense prerequisites such as ambient temperatures, as low as -20°C. Helwa et al. [34] studied a one-of-a-kind photo voltaic monitoring structures layout: a constant gadget going through south and tilted 40°, a vertical-axis tracker, a 6° tilted-axis tracker, and a two-axis tracker. Malla et al. [35] developed herbal thermosiphon SWHS at an excessive altitude lookup station with consequences validated with the TRNSYS model. Hematian et al. [36] targeted an estimation of experimental analyzed flat plate photo voltaic collector efficiency. [37-40] Patel Anand et al. [41] HD Chaudhary et al. [42-49] Patel Anand et al. evaluate various geometrical variations of absorber plate to enhance heat transfer efficiency in the solar heater. These studies are directly utilized in this research as well. The heat transfer enhancement phenomenon is performed in various applications such as [50, 51] Anand Patel et al. heat transfer devices [52, 53] Nikul Patel et al biofuels. The practical feasibility of solar heater are conceptualized using [54] S. Jaisankar et al. [55] N. V. Ogueke et al. [56] Ruchi Shukla et al. [57] Patel et al. The thermal performance enhancement for solar heaters is studied in [58] Hussain Al-Madani et al. Cylindrical Solar Water Heater [59] S. Vasanthaseelan et al. Different types of turbulators in a solar ware heater [60] S. Sathishkumar et al. historical solar water heating system work review paper. [61] Tengyue Wang et al. [62] Li et al. [63] Kime and Seo et al. [64] Pakdaman et al. document a thermal performance comparison between a solar air heater, a conventional tube collector, and a transparent tube collector which is helpful to perform the in the current study in comparison of Straight Tube and Square Tube Solar Water Heater.

2. Experimental Setup

In this article, a ½ inch copper pipe is made from two ½ inch L-shaped sections of 1 m in length, and these three pipes are made by brazing as shown in Plate 7 and Plate 8 with pipe length of 0.5 m square pipe top and bottom of these three pipes using brazing, and these two top and bottom pipes are connected by ½ inch round copper pipe which can be connected with PVC pipe. The PVC pipe is connected to the water tank. To absorb more heat, the pipes are painted black.

All the tubes are housed in a wooden box covered with an absorbing plate made of a 0.1mm thick galvanized steel sheet painted black, the upper part of which is covered with 2 mm thick transparent glass.

Figure 1 CAD Model of Experimental Setup

Figure 2 L shape copper sheet

Figure 3 Square Tube

Figure 4 Assembly of Solar Water Heater Pipe

Figure 5 End Connection of Solar Water Heater

Figure 6 Copper Pipes

Figure 7 Pipe Assembly of Solar water

Figure 8 Square Tube Solar Water Heater Experimental Setup

Figure 9 Straight Tube Solar Water Heater Experimental Setup

Similarly, with the same frame dimensions solar water heater is fabricated using three round copper pipes of $\frac{1}{2}$ " diameter at connect with $\frac{1}{2}$ " diameter copper pipe of 0.5 m length at the top and bottom. The K-type thermocouples are used to measure water inlet, outlet, and body temperature too in both experimental setups and using a 1 lt measuring flask with a stopwatch for flow measurement purposes.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the result of both experimental setups and Fig 10 represents temperature variation for time in both solar water heaters. Here square pipe of $\frac{1}{2}$ " square hole and a copper pipe of $\frac{1}{2}$ " through which water flows the interesting part is the cross-section area of the square pipe is more than 21 % circular pipe and so the time required for water is less than circular pipe and as the surface area on which radiation is incident is more in case of square tube solar water

heater and so better temperature results can be obtained in case of square tube solar water heater and so thermal performance is also better in case of square tube solar water heater.

Figure 10 Temperature Variation w.r.t Time

Table 1 Result Table

Time required to fill 1000 ml tank		Mass Flow Rate (Kg/s)		Heat Gain Qo kW		Heat Input Qi kW		Efficiency η	
Square	Straight	Square	Straight	Square	Straight	Square Tube	Straight	Square Tube	Straight
292	353	0.003	0.003	0.130	0.142	0.681	0.681	19.17	20.92
292	353	0.003	0.003	0.142	0.154	0.681	0.681	20.92	22.66
292	353	0.003	0.003	0.166	0.190	0.681	0.681	24.40	27.89
292	353	0.003	0.003	0.190	0.214	0.681	0.681	27.89	31.37
292	353	0.003	0.003	0.202	0.225	0.681	0.681	29.63	33.12
292	354	0.003	0.003	0.213	0.237	0.681	0.681	31.29	34.76
292	355	0.003	0.003	0.236	0.259	0.681	0.681	34.66	38.13
292	356	0.003	0.003	0.247	0.282	0.681	0.681	36.29	41.48
292	357	0.003	0.003	0.301	0.281	0.681	0.681	44.25	41.36

Nomenclature

T1 = inlet water Temperature in Straight Tube, T2 = Body Temperature in Straight Tube, T3 = water outlet Temperature in Straight Tube, T4= inlet water Temperature in Square Tube, T5= Body Temperature in Square Tube, T6= water outlet Temperature in Square Tube Qo = Heat gain Qi = Heat input

4. Conclusion

Thermal performance point of view this solar water heater is a better option but economically it is not viable due difficult to manufacture and the high cost of fabrication.

References

- [1] Soteris A. Kalogirou, Solar thermal collectors and applications, Progress in Energy and Combustion Science Volume 30, 2004.
- [2] Samara Sadrin, Maherin Hossain, Ehsanul Mohith Alternative solar water heater for domestic purpose, A Thesis Submitted BRAC University, 2009
- [3] P. Rhushi Prasad, H.V. Byregowda, P.B. Gangavati, “Experiment Analysis of Flat Plate Collector and Comparison of Performance with Tracking Collector” European Journal of Scientific Research, Volume 40 2010.
- [4] Wattana Ratismith, A Novel Non-Tracking Solar Collector for High Temperature Application., proceedings of ecos 2012 - the 25th international conference on efficiency, cost, optimization, simulation and environmental impact of energy systems 2012, perugia, italy.
- [5] Krisztina Uzuneanu, Alexandrina Teodoru, Tanase Panait ,Optimum Tilt Angle for Solar Collectors with Low Concentration Ratio, Advances in Fluid Mechanics and Heat & Mass Transfer, 2012
- [6] R. Herrero Martín, A. García Pinar, J. Pérez García Experimental heat transfer research in enhanced flatplate solar collectors ,World Renewable Energy Congress -2011, Sweden.
- [7] Mustafa AKTAS, Olhan CEYLAN, Hikmet DOGAN The Thermal Effectiveness Comparison of The Classical and Finned Solar System, J. of Thermal Science and Technology, Volume 26, 2006.
- [8] K. Sivakumar, N. Krishna Mohan and B. Sivaraman, Performance analysis of elliptical heat pipe solar collector, Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Volume 4, 2011.
- [9] S. Kalogirou, “Thermal performance, economic and environmental life cycle analysis of thermosiphon solar water heaters,” Solar Energy, Volume. 83, 2009.
- [10] C. Su, H. Madani, and B. Palm, “Heating solutions for residential buildings in China: current status and future outlook,” Energy Conversion and Management, Volume 177, 2018.
- [11] M. Souliotis, G. Panaras, P. A. Fokaidis, S. Papaefthimiou, and S. A. Kalogirou, “Solar water heating for social housing: energy analysis and life cycle assessment,” Energy and Buildings, Volume 169, 2018.
- [12] M. Fani and A. Sadreddin, “Solar assisted CCHP system, energetic, economic and environmental analysis, case study: educational office buildings,” Energy and Buildings, Volume. 136,, 2017.
- [13] L. Altoé, D. Oliveira Filho, J. C. Carlo, P. M. B. Monteiro, and I. T. A. Martins, “An analysis of the economic viability and greenhouse gas emissions reductions resulting from the use of solar water heaters in a typical Brazilian dwelling,” Latin American Journal of Energy Research, Volume. 4, 2017.
- [14] M. S. Hossain, A. K. Pandey, M. A. Tunio, J. Selvaraj, K. E Hoque, and N. A. Rahim, “Thermal and economic analysis of low-cost modified flat-plate solar water heater with parallel two-side serpentine flow,” Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry, Volume. 123, 2016.
- [15] A. Şerban, N. Bărbuță-Mișu, N. Ciucescu, S. Paraschiv, and S. Paraschiv, “Economic and environmental analysis of investing in solar water heating systems,” Sustainability, Volume. 8, 2016.
- [16] S. D. Fertahi, T. Bouhal, F. Gargab, A. Jamil, T. Kousksou, and A. Benbassou, “Design and thermal performance optimization of a forced collective solar hot water production system in Morocco for energy saving in residential buildings,” Solar Energy, Volume 160, 2018.
- [17] O. Ayadi and S. Al-Dahidi, “Comparison of solar thermal and solar electric space heating and cooling systems for buildings in different climatic regions,” Solar Energy, Volume. 188, 2019.
- [18] R. Alayi, A. Kasaeian, and F. Atabi, “Thermal analysis of parabolic trough concentration photovoltaic/thermal system for using in buildings,” Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy, vol. 38, no. 6, p. 13220, 2019.
- [19] Jignesh A. Patel Tejendra B. Patel Dr. Sadanand Namjoshi, Comparative Study of Thermal Performance of Spiral Tube Solar Water Heater with Straight Tube Solar Water Heater, International Journal for Scientific Research & Development| Volume 3, 2015
- [20] Hardik A. Parmar, Ravi K. Dayata, Dr. Sadanand Namjoshi, Experimental Investigation of Thermal Performance of Serpentine Solar Water Heater, International Journal for Scientific Research & Development| Volume. 3, 2015

- [21] P. P. Patil, Dr. D. S. Deshmukh, Design Considerations for Flat Plate Solar Water Heater System Vol.3, No. 2, June 2015 ISSN (Print) 2277-7261
- [22] S. Jaisankar, J. Ananth, S. Thulasic, S.T. Jayasuthakar, K.N. Sheeba, A comprehensive review on solar water heaters, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews Volume 15 2011.
- [23] Runsheng Tang, Yanbin Cheng, Maogang Wu, Zhimin Li, Yamei Yu, Experimental and modeling studies on thermosiphon domestic solar water heaters with flat-plate collectors at clear nights, Energy Conversion and Management Volume 51 2010.
- [24] Selmi, M., Al-Khawaja, M.J., and Marafia, A., Validation of CFD simulation for flat plate solar energy collector, Renewable Energy, Volume 33, pp. 383-387, 2008.
- [25] M. Z. H. Khan, M. R. Al-Mamun, S. Sikdar, P. K. Halder, and M. R. Hasan, Design, Fabrication, and Efficiency Study of a Novel Solar Thermal Water Heating System: Towards Sustainable Development, International Journal of Photoenergy, Volume 1, 2016.
- [26] H. I. Abu-Mulaweh, "Design and development of solar water heating system experimental apparatus," Global Journal of Engineering Education, Volume 14, 2012.
- [27] Sushil Tiwari, Dr. Himanshu Agrawal, A Review: Experimental performance study on solar water heating system for increasing heat transfer, IJARIE, Volume 5, 2019
- [28] Ho, C., Chen, T., and Tsai, C., Experimental and Theoretical Studies of Re-Cyclic Flat-Plate Solar Water Heaters Equipped With Rectangle Conduits, Renewable Energy, Volume 35, 2010
- [29] D Prakash, Thermal analysis of building roof assisted with water heater and insulation material, Indian Academy of Sciences, 2018.
- [30] S. Sadhishkumar, "Thermal performance of water-in-glass evacuated tube solar Collector with and without phase change material", Indian Journal Sciences, 20(2), 193-201, 2018.
- [31] Ankit S. Gujrathi, Sachin P. Ingale, Sudhir U. Patil, Analysis of Parabolic Trough Collector using Ansys Fluent Software, Volume 5, 2017.
- [32] Bajracharya T R & Shakya S R, Technology Analysis of Domestic Solar Water Heater Systems in Nepal: Needs a Revamp, in 8th National Convention and FEISCA Regional meet, Kathmandu, 3- 5 April 2003.
- [33] Bari S, Optimum orientation of domestic solar water heaters for the low latitude countries, Energy Conversion and Management, Volume 42, 2001.
- [34] Helwa N H, Bahgat A B G, El Shafee A M R & El Shenawy E T, Maximum collectable solar energy by different solar tracking systems, Energy Sources, Volume 22, 2000.
- [35] Fuller R J, Schwede D, Malla A & Zahnd A, Prediction of hot water usage in a solar heated community bathing centre in Nepal, in ISES Solar World Congress 2007, Beijing China, 18 - 21 September 2007.
- [36] Hematian A, Ajabshirchi Y & Bakhtiari A A, Experimental analysis of flat plate solar air collector efficiency, Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Volume 5, 2012.
- [37] Anand Patel and Sadanand Namjoshi, "Phase change material based solar water heater," International Journal of Engineering Science Invention., vol. 5, no. 8, August 2016.
- [38] Anand Patel, Divyesh Patel, Sadanand Namjoshi (2018); Thermal Performance Evaluation of Spiral Solar Air Heater; Int J Sci Res Publ 5(9) (ISSN: 2250-3153). <http://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-0915.php?rp=P454598>
- [39] Patel A, Parmar H, Namjoshi S 2016 Comparative thermal performance studies of serpentine tube solar water heater with straight tube solar water heater. IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE) 13 79–83.
- [40] Patel, Anand et al. "Thermal Performance Analysis of Fin Covered Solar Air Heater", "International Journal of Engineering Science and Futuristic Technology" (2017).
- [41] HD Chaudhary, SA Namjoshi, A Patel, Effect of Strip Insertion on Thermal Performance Evaluation in Evacuated Tube Solar Water Heater with Different Inner Tube Diameter REVISTA GEINTEC-GESTAO INOVACAO E TECNOLOGIAS, Volume 11, Issue 3, Page- 1842-1847.
- [42] Anand Patel. "Effect of Inclination on the Performance of Solar Water Heater." International Journal for Scientific Research and Development 11.3 (2023): 413-416.

- [43] Patel, Anand. "The Performance Investigation of Square Tube Solar Water Heater", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijedr.org), ISSN:2455-2631, Vol.8, Issue 6, page no.872 - 878, June-2023, Available :<http://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR2306123.pdf>
- [44] Anand Patel. ""Comparative Thermal Performance Investigation of Box Typed Solar Air heater with V Trough Solar Air Heater"". International Journal of Engineering Science Invention (IJESI), Vol. 12(6), 2023, PP 45-51. Journal DOI- 10.35629/6734".
- [45] Patel, Anand, et al. "Comparative Thermal Performance Evaluation of U Tube and Straight Tube Solar Water Heater." International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science (IJRES), vol. 11, no. 6, June 2023, pp. 346–52. www.ijres.org/index.html.
- [46] Patel, A., Namjoshi, Dr. S., & Singh, S. K. (2023). Comparative Experimental Investigation of Simple and V-Shaped Rib Solar Air Heater. International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), 11(6), 2455–6211. http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Anand_PatelYHv7.pdf
- [47] Anand Patel, "Comparative Thermal Performance Analysis of Circular and Triangular Embossed Trapezium Solar Cooker with and without Heat Storage Medium", International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), Volume 12 Issue 7, July 2023, pp. 376-380, <https://www.ijer.net/getabstract.php?paperid=SR23612004356>.
- [48] Patel, Anand. "Experimental Investigation of Oval Tube Solar Water Heater With Fin Cover Absorber Plate." International Journal of Enhanced Research in Science, Technology & Engineering, vol. 12, issue no. 7, July 2023, pp. 19–26, doi:10.55948/IJERSTE.2023.0704.
- [49] Patel, Anand. "Comparative Thermal Performance Evaluation of V-shaped Rib and WShape Rib Solar Air Heater." International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, vol. 14, issue no. 7, July 2023, pp. 1033–39.
- [50] Patel, AK, & Zhao, W. "Heat Transfer Analysis of Graphite Foam Embedded Vapor Chamber for Cooling of Power Electronics in Electric Vehicles." Proceedings of the ASME 2017 Heat Transfer Summer Conference. Volume 1: Aerospace Heat Transfer; Computational Heat Transfer; Education; Environmental Heat Transfer; Fire and Combustion Systems; Gas Turbine Heat Transfer; Heat Transfer in Electronic Equipment; Heat Transfer in Energy Systems. Bellevue, Washington, USA. July 9–12, 2017. V001T09A003. ASME. <https://doi.org/10.1115/HT2017-4731>
- [51] Anand Patel, "Thermal Performance Investigation of Twisted Tube Heat Exchanger", International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), Volume 12 Issue 6, June 2023, pp. 350-353, <https://www.ijer.net/getabstract.php?paperid=SR23524161312>, DOI: 10.21275/SR23524161312.
- [52] Nikul K. Patel, Anand K. Patel, Ragesh G. Kapadia, Shailesh N. Shah, Comparative Study of Production and Performance of Bio-fuel Obtained from Different Non-edible Plant Oils, International Journal of Energy Engineering, Vol. 5 No. 3, 2015, pp. 41-47. doi: 10.5923/j.ijee.20150503.01.
- [53] Nikul K Patel , Padamanabhi S Nagar , Shailesh N Shah , Anand K Patel , Identification of Non-edible Seeds as Potential Feedstock for the Production and Application of Bio-diesel, Energy and Power, Vol. 3 No. 4, 2013, pp. 67-78. doi: 10.5923/j.ep.20130304.05.
- [54] S. Jaisankar, J. Ananth, S. Thulasi, S.T. Jayasuthakar, K.N. Sheeba, A comprehensive review on solar water heaters, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 15, Issue 6, 2011, Pages 3045-3050, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.03.009>.
- [55] N. V. Ogueke; E. E. Anyanwu; O. V. Ekechukwu , A review of solar water heating systems, , Information Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy 1, 043106 (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3167285>.
- [56] Ruchi Shukla, K. Sumathy, Phillip Erickson, Jiawei Gong, Recent advances in the solar water heating systems: A review, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 19, 2013, Pages 173-190, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.10.048>.
- [57] Patel et al., IJAET/Vol.III/ Issue IV/Oct.-Dec. 2012/146-149, REVIEW OF SOLAR WATER HEATING SYSTEMS.
- [58] Hussain Al-Madani, The performance of a cylindrical solar water heater, Renewable Energy, Volume 31, Issue 11, 2006, Pages 1751-1763, ISSN 0960-1481, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2005.09.010>.
- [59] S. Vasanthaseelan, P. Manoj Kumar, R. Anandkumar, K. Hari Ram, Ram Subbiah, V. Suresh, A.S. Abishek, R. Anith, P. Aravinth, S.V. Balaji, Investigation on solar water heater with different types of turbulators, Materials Today: Proceedings, Volume 47, Part 15, 2021, Pages 5203-5208, ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.05.530>.

- [60] S. Sathishkumar, T. Balusamy, Performance improvement in solar water heating systems—A review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 37, 2014, Pages 191-198, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.04.072>.
- [61] Tengyue Wang, Yanhua Diao, Yaohua Zhao, Lin Liang, Zeyu Wang, Chuanqi Chen, A comparative experimental investigation on thermal performance for two types of vacuum tube solar air collectors based on flat micro-heat pipe arrays (FMHPA), *Solar Energy*, Volume 201, 2020, Pages 508-522, ISSN 0038-092X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.03.024>.
- [62] Li et al., 2017 S.L. Li, H. Wang, X.R. Meng, X.L. We, Comparative study on the performance of a new solar air collector with different surface shapes, *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, 114 (2017), pp. 639-644.
- [63] Kim and Seo, 2007 Y. Kim, T. Seo, Thermal performances comparisons of the glass evacuated tube solar collectors with shapes of absorber tube, *Renew Energy*, 32 (5) (2007), pp. 772-795.
- [64] Pakdaman et al., 2011 M.F. Pakdaman, A. Lashkari, H.B. Tabrizi, R. Hosseini, Performance evaluation of a natural-convection solar air-heater with a rectangular-finned absorber plate, *Energy Convers. Manage.*, 52 (2) (2011), pp. 1215-1225.